

Construction of a focused ultrasound neuromodulation system for the treatment of epileptic seizure

Minjian Zhang, Rongyu Tang, Yiran Lang, Jiping He

Abstract: Thus far, Ultrasound has been proved to be useful for noninvasively stimulating brain activity and has hope to play a positive role in the treatment of neurological diseases. Epilepsy is a neurological disorder in which brain activity becomes abnormal, causing seizures or periods of unusual behavior, and sometimes loss of awareness. In this paper, we established a focused ultrasound (FUS) neuromodulation system for the treatment of epilepsy. We used the chemically-induced rat epilepsy model to explore the effect of pulsed focused ultrasound on epilepsy, and obtained preliminary experimental results. We have proved the feasibility of this system through experiments, which can be used in the treatment of epilepsy by ultrasound neuromodulation.

Keywords: Ultrasound; Neuromodulation; epilepsy

I. INTRODUCTION

Epilepsy is a transient functional disorder of the brain attributed to uncontrollable abnormal hyperexcitability of neurons. It is a chronic disease with seizures as the main manifestation of persistent or secondary changes in the brain and triggers neurophysiology, psychology, and society [1]. Epileptic seizure is usually difficult to be predicted, and epilepsy is difficult to cure. Drug therapy and surgical treatment are the two main means of anti-epilepsy. Medication is currently considered the most effective method, and more than half of epilepsy can be controlled with drugs, for example phenobarbital, phenytoin, carbamazepine and sodium valproate [2]. However, most anti-epileptic drugs have obvious toxic side effects on liver and kidney function. Surgical resection of epileptic foci is a shortcut for epileptic seizures with limited drug effect. Because surgical resection of epileptic foci can basically control the vast majority of major episodes and the fundamental problem of some focal epilepsy, but surgery has high requirements for accurate localization of epileptic foci and preoperative assessment [3]. Antiepileptic drugs are needed to actively prevent and control postoperative complications, and many patients still refuse surgical treatment due to fear of risk and postoperative sequela. At present, with the development of stereotactic technology, non-invasive methods such as

gamma knife, transcranial magnetic stimulation (TMS) are also actively explored the treatment of epilepsy, including vagal nerve stimulation and deep brain stimulation, but its positioning accuracy and the effective cure rate is not optimal [4].

Ultrasound (US) is an acoustic wave as one of mechanical pressure waves which is named because its lower frequency limit is greater than the human hearing limit (> 20 kHz). Since US can be propagated over long distances in a particular medium and the energy attenuation is very small, it is widely used in medical diagnostics and physiotherapy. Ultrasonic neuromodulation for brain stimulation has its irreplaceable advantages. It does not need genetic alteration or surgery, but it provides spatial resolutions superior to other noninvasive methods such as TMS or tDCS. Ultrasonic neuromodulation is safer and easier to achieve than Optogenetics. And ultrasonic neuromodulation is more eligible than other noninvasive methods for the deep brain stimulation [5]. Several experiments of the effects of focused ultrasound stimulation on the ex vivo animal brain have verified that ultrasound can temporarily modify the excitability of the neuronal tissue [6], which is possibly mediated by the regulation of ion channels without raising the local tissue temperature [7]. Ultrasound is also known to decrease cortical excitability, as it has been demonstrated by concurrent monitoring of visual evoked potentials in cats [8]. The modulation was achieved without altering the tissue

Corresponding Author: Minjian Zhang. Beijing Institute of Technology, Beijing, China, E-mail: zmj_921023@outlook.com

temperature. By taking advantage of such a modulatory property of the pulsed ultrasound, especially to decrease the excitability, we had the motivation to further explore if the focused ultrasound could have a positive inhibition on the epileptic seizure.

Considering that ultrasound has shown excellent effects in the field of neuromodulation in recent years, the purpose of the study was to establish a focused ultrasound neuromodulation system for the treatment of epilepsy, and explore the effect of FUS on epileptic seizure, which was induced by the intraperitoneal injection of kanic acid (KA) into SD rats. Kanic acid is a cyclic analog l-glutamate and a potent agonist for kainite receptors that can lead to status epilepticus in animals, has been extensively used in animal models to study epilepsy [9]. A single dose of KA can increase neuronal excitability across the entire brain volume with dominant hyper-excitability and induce an acute stage of epilepsy. In this paper, we successfully built a focused ultrasound neuromodulation system used for the treatment of epilepsy and independently developed a kind of 32-channel EEG electrode. We used pulsed ultrasound to simulate the entire thalamic area of rats with KA-induced acute epileptic seizure and measured electroencephalogram (EEG) activity to evaluate the degree of epileptic activity with the self-developed 32-channel EEG electrode.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Experimental grouping

All procedures with rats were approved by the Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee of Beijing Institute of Technology. Male Sprague-Dawley rats (300 ± 50 g prior to the epilepsy induction; $n = 18$) were randomly divided into two groups. The rats in Group 1 (induction of acute epilepsy via KA injection) were treated with pulsed focused ultrasound on the brain after KA-administration ($n = 9$). The goal of this group was to explore the effects of sonication on an acute seizure model. Group 2 (KA injected rats without sonication; $n = 9$) provided a control condition to evaluate the EEG features of KA-induced epilepsy without sonication. EEG signals were synchronously recorded throughout the whole procedure.

B. Electrode positioning and implantation

We used self-developed 32 channels EEG electrode to record the EEG signals throughout the whole

procedure. In order to have enough position of the ultrasound transducer to fit the skull, we deliberately vacated the 4th, 6th, 8th, 26th, 28th, and 30th channels, and then fixed the electrodes on the skull surface through the skull nails on the remaining channels. After the electrode was fixed, we used a special adapter to connect the electrode to the signal acquisition device. The rat was fixed on the stereotaxic apparatus (RWD life science E03135-001) and the Gas Evacuation Apparatus (RWD life science R546W) was used to continue the anesthesia throughout the whole procedure without interruption. A temperature controller was used to remain proper body temperature throughout the experiments. One week after the EEG electrode implantation surgery, the recovery of the rats was determined, and the ultrasound stimulation test would be performed if the recovery was well. The physical diagram and circuit diagram of the electrode can be seen in Fig. 1. The first picture and the second picture are the physical and circuit diagrams of the electrode, and the part inside the red frame is the position reserved for the ultrasound transducer. The third and fourth pictures show the rat after the electrode was implanted.

Fig. 1 (a) Self-developed 32-channel EEG electrode. (b) Details of the electrode array. (c-d) The rat implanted with the electrode.

C. Focused ultrasound sonication setup

All FUS experiments were conducted with a low intensity focused ultrasound (LIFU) transducer with a 0.5 MHz center frequency (35 mm focal depth, 20 mm in dia; Goworld, Guangdong, China). This frequency is applicable for transcranial applications whereby the frequency range of 440 to 700 KHz has an optimal transmission gain through the ex vivo human skull [10,11]. The driving signal was derived from a two-channel waveform generator (33500B, Keysight Technologies Inc., Santa Rosa, CA, USA) and amplified through a RF amplifier (North Star model SWA200D RF power amplifier, The Institute of Acoustics of the Chinese Academy of Sciences). FG1

was used to trigger US pulses, establish the pulse-repetition frequency (PRF) and define the number of pulses (np) in an ultrasound neuromodulation stimulus waveform. FG2 was used to establish the acoustic frequency (Af) and the number of cycles per pulse (c.p.p.). The transducer was calibrated with a fiber optic hydrophone (PT-1711395, The Institute of Acoustics of the Chinese Academy of Sciences). We used an oscilloscope (MSOX2022A, Keysight Technologies Inc., Santa Rosa, CA, USA) to help observe. Example of the FUS waveform used in this paper is shown in Fig. 3 with the following properties: Af= 0.5MHz, c.p.p. = 150, PRF = 1.5kHz, np = 200.

Fig. 2 Basic ultrasonic brain stimulation rig. (a) 500 KHz US transducer used for FUS. (b) A fiber optic hydrophone. (c) A two-channel waveform generator and a RF amplifier. (d) An oscilloscope.

Fig. 3 Pulsed ultrasound waveform generation.

D. Induction of epilepsy and FUS sonication

Rats were housed in rooms with 12 h light/dark cycles and provided food and water ad lib. One week

after electrode implantation, The EEG signal was amplified and recorded at a sampling rate of 1000 Hz. The EEG signal was recorded for ten minutes to establish the baseline condition. 6.5mg/kg (based on animal weight) of KA solution was administered to the animals in Groups 1 and 2 via intraperitoneal injection. The ultrasound transducer was fixed over the rat skull, an acoustic collimator was filled with US gel transmit US waveforms to restricted brain regions [5]. Once the transducer and acoustic collimator had been coupled to the rat head, EEG was subsequently acquired for ten minutes after there was significant evidence of the epileptic behaviors (e.g., Hind limb convulsion). The first dose of FUS sonication was then delivered to the animals for three times. The EEG signals were measured after the first sonication for additional ten minutes. The second dose of FUS sonication was then administered to the animals for additional three times, followed by EEG monitoring for another ten minutes. The third dose of FUS sonication was then administered to the animals for additional three times, followed by EEG monitoring for another ten minutes. Upon the completion of the procedure, the animal was returned back to the cage for recovery. Fig. 3 is a schematic view of the experimental apparatus. Fig. 4 shows the rat which was induced by KA into epileptic seizure undergoing focused ultrasound treatment.

Fig. 4 The schematic view of the experimental apparatus.

Fig. 5 The rat induced by KA into epileptic seizure

undergoing pulsed focused ultrasound treatment.

E. EEG data analysis

We used EEGLab for EEG data preprocessing, the pretreatment mainly included the electrode positioning, signal bandpass filtering, channel selection, etc. We used a bandpass filter of 0.5-40Hz based on the frequency range of the EEG signal and removed the channels that were not well recorded. Finally, we got preliminary results. Exemplary EEG data acquired from one animal within each group (Groups 1 and 2) are shown in results below.

III. RESULTS

In the final signal processing, we removed 8 channels that were affected by the ultrasound transducer and recorded poorly, and finally used 24 channels of signals for data analysis. Prior to the KA injection, there was no apparent detection of epileptic EEG signal bursts. Within approximately 40 minutes after the administration of KA, epileptic signal bursts were observed in their EEG recordings. Before the epileptic seizure, we can see the normal sleep EEG signal. As shown in Fig. 6 and Fig. 7, there is no significant difference in the sleep EEG signals before epileptic seizure and the signals after epileptic seizure 10mins between the rats in Group 1 and Group 2. As demonstrated in Fig. 8, we intercepted the EEG signal of the rat in group 2 for 10 seconds in the same time period as the rat in group 1, we intercepted the EEG signal of the rat in group 2 for 10 seconds in the same time period as the rat in group 1. It can be seen that the number of EEG bursts of the rat which did not receive sonication in group 2 appeared to be more than the number of bursts of the rat received three ultrasound stimulations. This indicates that the three ultrasound stimulations we performed may have an effect on the inhibition of epileptic seizure

Fig. 6 Sleep EEG signals of rats in two groups before epileptic seizure.

Fig. 7 Comparison of EEG signals of two groups after epileptic seizure 40mins.

III. DISCUSSION

Our results reveal that pulsed focused ultrasound decreased epileptic signal bursts observed in EEG recordings after the induction of acute epilepsy via intraperitoneal injection of KA. Thus, our research may provide a new solution for the treatment of epilepsy. Taken together, these findings suggest that transcranial FUS sonication provided a significant suppressive effect on KA-induced epileptic activity in rats. These observations are in good agreement with previous studies on the temporary suppression of spontaneous activity in the excised crayfish ventral nerve cord [12] and on the suppression of visual activity in cats mediated through insonication of non-focused ultrasound [13]. Although the inferior colliculus of rats is responsive to ultrasound [14] and can even induce audiogenic seizures [15, 16], our observations are unlikely to be associated with the auditory responsiveness of the inferior colliculus of rats to ultrasound frequencies. This is because the ultrasound frequency of the present study (e.g., 500 KHz) was far greater than the audible range (applicable to rodents, approximately 30 to 70 KHz) of ultrasound frequencies in which the maximal responsiveness of the inferior colliculus of rats was observed [14].

We have successfully built a focused ultrasound neuromodulation system and in the future research work, we are going to how to use this platform for treatment of epilepsy and strive for better results. We have the

following points to be improved. First of all, we will try to use computer control system to change the parameters of the ultrasound transducer and ultrasound sequence to further improve the FUS neuromodulation system and explore whether different parameters have different effects on the regulation of epilepsy. Another technical limitation is the positioning of focused ultrasound in the brain. Because it is affected by the skull and brain tissue, we are currently unable to accurately locate ultrasound in the brain tissue, but magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) may help us solve this problem.

In addition, since the intraperitoneal injection of KA elicits hyper-excitability over the distributed regions of the brain, region-specific anti-epileptogenic effects of FUS were not demonstrated. In order to examine the utility of FUS in suppressing region-specific epileptogenic activity, we will have a try make a regional chemical kindling model by an intracortical injection of KA, which can be adopted to induce focal epileptic lesions in an animal model. Intracortical injection of KA induces nonconvulsive status epilepticus and caused massive temporal and hippocampal damage [17-19]. And we will add a control group to study the effects of low-frequency focused ultrasound on brain tissue to ensure that the energy produced by ultrasound does not cause mechanical damage to brain tissue.

Through group experiment, we used the KA-induced rat epilepsy model to explore the effect of pulsed focused ultrasound on epilepsy, and obtained preliminary experimental results. We have proved the feasibility of this system through experiments, which can be used in the treatment of epilepsy by ultrasound neuromodulation. There are still many unknown places to explore and improve on the study of ultrasound neuromodulation in the treatment of epilepsy. In future research work, we will make full use of this system to further explore ultrasound neuromodulation

REFERENCES

- [1] Brodie MJ, Elder AT, Kwan P, "Epilepsy in later life." *Lancet Neurol*, vol. 8, no. 11, pp. 1019-1030, 2009.
- [2] Perucca E, Tomson T, "The pharmacological treatment of epilepsy in adults." *Lancet Neurol*, vol.10, no.5, pp. 446-456, 2011.
- [3] Cascino, G. D. "Surgical Treatment for Extratemporal Epilepsy." *Current Treatment Options in Neurology*, vol.6, no.3, pp. 257-262, 2004.
- [4] Wagner T, Valero-Cabre A, Pascual-Leone A, "Noninvasive human brain stimulation." *Annu Rev Biomed Eng*, vol.9, pp. 527-565, 2007.
- [5] Tufail, Yusuf, et al. "Ultrasonic neuromodulation by brain stimulation with transcranial ultrasound." *NATURE PROTOCOL*, vol. 6, no.9, pp. 1453-1470, 2011.
- [6] Jolesz FA, Hynynen K, McDannold N, Tempany C, "MR imaging-controlled focused ultrasound ablation: a noninvasive image-guided surgery." *Magn Reson Imaging Clin N AM*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 545-560, 2005.
- [7] Gavrilov LR, Tsurulnikov EM, Davies IA, "Application of focused ultrasound for the stimulation of neural structures." *Ultrasound Med Biol*, vol. 22, no. 2, pp. 179-192, 1996.
- [8] Tyler WJ, Tufail Y, Finsterwald M, Tauchmann ML, Olson EJ, Majestic C, "Remote excitation of neuronal circuits using low-intensity, lowfrequency ultrasound Remote excitation of neuronal circuits using low-intensity, low frequency ultrasound." *Plos One*, vol. 3, no. 10, 2008
- [9] Hubbard, Jacqueline A., and D. K. Binder, "Preface." *Astrocytes & Epilepsy*, vol.30, pp. 197-224, 2016.
- [10] Ekstrand JJ, Domroese ME, Johnson DM, Feig SL, Knodel SM, Behan M, Haberly LB, "A new subdivision of anterior piriform cortex and associated deep nucleus with novel features of interest for olfaction and epilepsy." *J Comp Neurol*, vol. 434, no. 3, pp. 289-307, 2001.
- [11] White PJ, "Transcranial focused ultrasound surgery." *Top Magn Reson Imaging*, vol. 17, no. 3, pp. 165-172, 2006.
- [12] Fry WJ, Wulff VJ, Tucker D, Fry FJ, "Physical factors involved in ultrasonically induced changes in living systems: 1. Identification of non-temperature effects." *Acoust Soc Am*, vol. 22, pp. 641-652, 1950.
- [13] Fry FJ, Ades HW, Fry WJ, "Production of reversible changes in the central nervous system by ultrasound." *Science*, vol.127, no. 3289, pp. 83-84, 1958.
- [14] Brown AM, "High levels of responsiveness from the inferior colliculus of rodents at ultrasonic frequencies." *J Comp Physiol*, vol. 83, pp. 393-406, 1973.
- [15] Zrull MC, Coleman JR, "Effects of tectal grafts on sound location deficits at ultrasonic frequencies." *Exp Neurol*, vol. 145, no. 1, pp. 16-23,1997.
- [16] Coleman JR, Gibson CJ, Fourqurean GD, Ross KC, "Tectal graft modulation of audiogenic seizures in Long-Evans rat." *Experimental Neurology*, vol. 164, no. 1, pp. 0-144, 2000.
- [17] Gouder, Nicolette, F. Jean-Marc, and D. Boison, "Seizure Suppression by Adenosine A₁ Receptor Activation in a Mouse Model of Pharmacoresistant Epilepsy." *Epilepsia*, vol. 44, no. 7, pp. 877-885, 2003.
- [18] Riban, V, et al., "Evolution of hippocampal epileptic activity during the development of hippocampal sclerosis in a mouse model of temporal lobe epilepsy." *Neuroscience*, vol. 112, no. 1, pp. 101-111, 2002.
- Heinrich C, et al, "Reelin Deficiency and Displacement of Mature Neurons, But Not Neurogenesis, Underlie the Formation of Granule Cell Dispersion in the Epileptic Hippocampus." *Journal of Neuroscience*, vol.